

The Impermanence of Location: Is Seychelles drifting closer to the Middle East?

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Geographical location – measured in the universal language of latitude and longitude – might at first seem to be one of few fixed points in an otherwise changing world. Places are where they are and one can find them on a map. The capital of Seychelles can be found at 4°37' south of the equator and 55°27' east of the meridian line. In fact, I am going to argue that this is not quite so; location is not necessarily what it first seems.

Other factors come into play which change the meaning of location. *Time*, for instance, is an obvious variable. With increasingly rapid modes of transport, the world has become smaller; distance has been shrunk and, in terms of journey times, places are now closer to each other than they once were. Another factor is *connectivity*. For instance, a nation's trading patterns, security issues and alliances can all close the gap between otherwise distant locations. They seem closer to each other than they were, because they are. The critical factor is no longer what is literal but the intervention of *perception*.

In this presentation I argue that, although Seychelles has seemingly stayed where it always was, it can no longer be regarded as a remote archipelago with little contact to the outside world. It is this duality of being a fixed point in space combined with a different meaning that I call *the impermanence of location*. As well as providing some examples of how this impermanence has been evident over a relatively long period, I focus on the implications of ongoing conflicts in the Middle East. My argument is that Seychelles is shifting ever closer along a geopolitical path towards the epicentre of that troubled region. And I suggest eight ways in which one can see this happening.

1. Continental drift

Purists will argue that even so-called fixed points are not necessarily permanent. Specifically, the earth's surface contains tectonic plates which, in effect, slide from one position to another, taking different land masses with them. This process, which explains the present through the distant past, will normally continue over millions of years. It is hardly evident in a lifetime, except in areas of immediate instability, where earthquakes and other ground movements give the game away. As an example of continental drift, Australia is on a collision course with Indonesia – but at the rate of a few centimetres a year it will take 30 million years to get there. Australians have plenty of time to prepare for the event.

About 1,800 million years ago, a vast 'super continental' land mass – extending from South America to Australia – started to break up. Most of the resultant pieces (including the one known as Gondwanaland) were on a continental scale but some broke off in smaller fragments. One of the latter was left behind to form the Seychelles islands, with their distinctive granitic peaks rising from the deep ocean, seemingly unconnected to anywhere else. Mauritius, to the south, shares the same continental shelf but even that neighbouring island is more than a thousand miles away, much the same as the distance to mainland Africa. As such, the modern history of Seychelles was marked by isolation.

Such was its distance from anywhere else, its islands scattered far out in the western Indian Ocean, that the archipelago remained uninhabited until well into the eighteenth century, almost certainly one of the last places on earth to be so. That is not to say there was no human contact before. It is believed that Arab dhows plying the east coast of Africa called in to replenish supplies of fresh water and to add stocks of fish, vegetables and fruit to be found in and around the islands. So, too, the Portuguese explorers, whose sights were set on more distant destinations to the east, also made landings in order to restock. But neither Arabs nor Portuguese saw any reason to stay.

2. Colonial ties

It was left to France in 1770 to start a process of permanent settlement. On claiming the islands as French territory, their own nationals carved out large estates from the wilderness

and brought in slave labour from Madagascar and continental Africa. When the French, by international treaty following the demise of Napoleon's empire, had to cede control in 1814, the British took over. At least to start with, they also relied on forced (and then indentured) labour to work on the plantations, remaining in charge until independence was granted in 1976. So, for a little more than 200 years, Seychelles was a European colony – governed, in turn, by countries thousands of miles away on a different continent. Its location was effectively split between the immediacy of the islands and colonial offices in Paris and London. And the legacy includes the fact that, since independence, two of the three official languages are French and English.

In the course of that era, in addition to the instruments of colonial control, isolation was gradually reduced as a result of regular (although initially infrequent) shipping connections and, by the end of the nineteenth century, cable and wireless links. Of course, in one sense the location of the colony was unchanged, firmly based a few degrees south of the equator. But, in another way, this was already beginning to mean something quite different. The colony had become inextricably linked to the rest of the world. Inhabitants would still think of their tropical home as being remote, with only a monthly supply ship and often unpredictable passenger stops on the route from Bombay to Mombasa, but even such tenuous connections were enough to shape the future of the islands. And this proved to be only the start of a new era of global communication.

3. Ideological links

During the Second World War, a number of Seychellois joined the British army in the struggle against the Nazis, returning to tell their families of faraway places. One might have thought the world had experienced enough of war but, instead, in 1945 new divisions opened up to usher in what is known as the Cold War. This time it was not so much the direct use of weapons which divided nations but the threat of doing so, including the potential of nuclear warfare. Countries divided along ideological lines, according to communist or capitalist leanings.

So where was Seychelles when all this was taking place? Even if it had wanted to remain in splendid isolation – an oceanic utopia – it would have been unable to do so. More powerful nations had their own priorities, seeing in this collection of islands strategic value as a landing point in the western Indian Ocean. International powers like China, Russia, France and the UK (but not India, which argued that non-aligned countries should not take sides) intervened on one side or the other. The ideological alignment of Seychelles with the Soviet bloc also encouraged the direct involvement of Libya and Cuba, which both established embassies in Victoria. And in a symbolic act to show his Marxist credentials, former president Albert René chose a North Korean team to form his personal bodyguard. But René was duplicitous and while he would greet Russian warships in Victoria harbour he would also collect rent from the Americans, who continued to use their listening post on high ground on Mahé (where the tourism academy is presently located).

4. Rights of passage

The distance between Victoria and Mogadishu is more than 800 miles of open sea. In the first decade of the present century, it became the scene of pirate attacks. Seychelles was not itself the main target for piracy but was brought into the situation in two ways – because of the impact the attacks were having on tourist yachts in its own seas, and as a result of interference with the international shipping route from north to south off the eastern coast of Africa. It was the latter which led to other nations joining Seychelles in a task force to protect their shared rights of navigation. Quite simply, the actions of pirates – who typically boarded and overpowered large container and other ships from small but fast skiffs – were effective in disrupting traffic and raising costs of transporting cargo. This had an immediate impact on Seychelles, raising the prices of imported goods, but there were also repercussions for countries far afield.

Seychelles took the initiative in alerting other nations to the problem and calling for common action. In the course of doing this, the 800 miles to Somalia was effectively reduced; like it or not, the small island state became a regional, if not international, player in the Indian Ocean. Such was the influence of Seychelles that (as part of a rotation of responsibilities) it was asked at one stage to provide a chairperson for the task force (which included representatives of major powers like India, China and the US).

Although no longer (until recently) making headlines, the threat of further piracy continues and foreign navies remain active in supporting a policy of containment to prevent renewed attacks. The outcome of all this is that, in strategic terms, Seychelles is effectively closer now to Somalia and the Horn of Africa than it used to be. From the day when the then president of Seychelles, James Michel, condemned Somalia as a failed state, the old adage of being a friend of all and an enemy of none was consigned to a more optimistic chapter of history. In fact, one can argue that it had already been negated by the alignment of Seychelles within the Soviet bloc during the Cold War.

5. Global interconnections

Within a generation, globalization changed everything. Even within the first decades of the present century, Seychelles was firmly plugged into the international economy. There are myriad connections and interconnections in all realms of economic and social activity – from finance to trade, education to invention. Staying out of this arena of frenzied activity is not an option. No one can afford to be left out.

I suspect that everyone in this room has the means to communicate with more or less anywhere else in the world. In the ten years I have been here, the roads have become busy with traffic; there are now more than 40,000 cars on the roads, up from 30,000 in 2018. One hardly needs official figures to see, on an everyday basis, that housebuilding has increased exponentially. And each day planes fly into the international airport, mainly to

bring in tourists from a growing number of countries. In a way that would never have been imagined by our predecessors, we are presently sitting in an air-conditioned room close to the equator, enjoying the luxury of exchanging ideas. Yes, there are still problems resulting from reliance on imports but, overall, it would hardly be accurate to describe this small island state as any longer remote. Or at least not in the traditional sense. Seychelles is an integral part of the world community; physically, it is where it has been since the days of Gondwanaland but its *meaning* has changed. In effect, Seychelles is now closer than it was to Chinese factories, Middle Eastern oil, European finance markets, and American television and film production.

6. Ocean realignments

A new security map is being drawn, with the Indo-Pacific emerging as one of the most active areas of economic and military rivalry. And, like it or not, Seychelles has a place in this changing world order.

America came and left, and then in 2023 returned in the face of the growing naval presence of China in the Indian Ocean. As a trading partner in the region, Sri Lanka set up a high commission in 2014. So, too, offices have been opened for the diplomats of Japan and the United Arab Emirates. Valuable fish reserves in the surrounding seas, coupled with the potential of seabed mineral rights and its popularity as a tourist venue, have added to the international attraction of Seychelles.

However, in the tangled world of geopolitics, it is the global spread of power and influence which accounts for this unmistakable upsurge of interest in what was once aspired to as a potential zone of peace. As I have already indicated, gone are the days when Seychelles could claim that it was completely neutral. That was an appealing maxim that worked for a while but is no longer tenable. Like a child who becomes an adult, Seychelles now has responsibilities of its own. When India (with the world's largest population) sought to establish a garrison and landing facilities on the outer island of Assumption, Seychelles (with little more than 100,000 people) rejected the overture. No one doubts that there were diplomatic costs in doing so but as a sign of independence the price of sovereignty was deemed worth it.

In a different relationship with a great power, whenever a vote is taken in the United Nation on the issue of Taiwan's legitimacy, Seychelles lines up behind China, knowing that if it does not do so it will no longer be a beneficiary of the Asian giant's largesse. Making a speech on the occasion of China's new year in 2024, President Ramkalawan took the opportunity once again to reinforce the continuing support of Seychelles.

There is also a special relationship with the UAE. The royal family of the desert state enjoy periods spent in Seychelles, facilitated by helpful planning permissions for their extravagant residences and direct access to senior decision makers. In turn, Seychelles

benefits from generous grants and donations to assist infrastructure development. And each day, as if to reflect the special relationship, two of the world's foremost airlines – Emirates and Etihad land at the country's international airport, bringing in more tourists as well as cargo. Bonds with the Middle East are strengthened.

Such is the world of diplomacy, a trading floor where favours are exchanged and rewards given. Like it or not, Seychelles has no option but to be a part of this. In what is nearly half a century since it gained independence, it has become an international player in its own right. The map that can be drawn today is already very different from that of 1976. From its role as an almost invisible supplier of vanilla, cinnamon and other tropical spices, it has assumed a prominent place on the map of the western Indian Ocean. For better or worse, it has drifted from where it was into the geopolitical mainstream. In effect, through its numerous connections it now occupies a new – and more exposed – location. To date, however, it is not entirely clear whether this change has brought with it an updated foreign relations strategy. Is its changing position in the world a result of chance or design? And, if design, how should it locate itself?

7. Below the radar

As well as more publicized issues that are drawing Seychelles closer to the Middle East, there are other, less obvious, threads that together strengthen the connection.

- ◆ Like many other nations, Seychelles is dependent on a supply of oil from the Gulf states. In spite of the potential of renewable sources like solar, wind and wave power, oil and natural gas account for 95% of the country's consumption. With the Middle East the nearest major source, it is understandable that there is a regular shipping route between the two locations.
- ◆ Less acceptable is another busy line of traffic, in this case in the form of the illegal importation of hard drugs from Iran, and also Pakistan to the north, and the thriving market in Seychelles. Originating in Afghanistan, drugs are brought to the Indian Ocean ports in that region and then out in dhows for mid-ocean rendezvous with fast craft which collect their latest consignment before returning to Seychelles. Only a small number of incoming boats are intercepted.
- ◆ A third example stems from an agreement with Israel for regular flights to Tel Aviv and the promotion of Seychelles as a safe tourist destination. Formal diplomatic relations between the two countries were opened in 1992 and since then there has been a steady increase in two-way traffic. Unfortunately, an initiative launched in 2020 to support further interaction was badly affected by Covid and, more recently it has been brought to a halt by the conflict in Gaza.

- ◆ Another link to the Middle East (stimulated by the presence of Emirates and Etihad, and also Qatar airlines) results from Seychellois making trips to Dubai and other cities in the region for shopping expeditions and short vacations. Offers are frequently advertised in the local press. Just as the UAE royals travel to Seychelles to escape the desert heat, our own citizens look for opportunities to make up for the lack of shopping and entertainment facilities locally.

8. Running the gauntlet

It is time now to focus on ongoing events. My argument is that, in the face of currents of change, Seychelles is being swept far out to sea – in the direction of the Middle East. The Gulf states remain at least a four-hour flight away but the real distance is starting to feel a good deal closer.

I have already referred to the presence of Somalian pirates in the region but now, triggered by the conflict in Gaza between Israel and Hamas, interference with shipping has been extended over a much wider area and involving different parties. What, you might ask, has this to do with Seychelles? The answer is that conflicts have a nasty habit of spreading beyond the original epicentre. Not only has the present crisis in Gaza quickly become an international issue, with different nations taking sides, but as with the incidence of piracy off the coast of Somalia, the rights of shipping to enjoy free navigation is once again at issue.

Take account of geography

To understand this, we need to look at the geography of the north-western Indian Ocean and, in particular, the two narrow extensions – one, the Persian Gulf and the other the Red Sea. Both are natural features with strategic implications but, in the present situation, it is the Red Sea which is drawing most attention.

In spite of its separate name, the Red Sea is an inseparable part of the Indian Ocean. But it is a sea with a difference, and one can immediately note that it extends north-westwards to within a short distance of the neighbouring Mediterranean. In some ways it almost resembles a long linear-shaped lake, extending over a distance of 1400 miles, generally no more than 200 miles across but at its southern end narrowing to the Bab el-Mendeb, barely 20 miles from shore to shore. Its unusual structure is explained by the fact that it is part of the Great East African Rift Valley, which comprises a chain of separate geological systems, starting in Lebanon in the north and continuing south through to Mozambique.

Within this sub-region of the Middle East, there are three potential trigger points:

- ◆ One is the existence of the Suez Canal in the northern reaches of the Red Sea. It hardly needs satellite imagery to show how close this is to the Mediterranean, and thence to Europe. This was evident even from the time of the ancient civilizations in the region. Some 2,600 years ago the Egyptian king, Necho II, created a link between the waters of the Nile and the Red Sea, naming it rather grandly the Canal of the Pharaohs. A century later, Darius I led an invading army into the region from Persia and, largely ignoring what had been achieved before him, ordered the construction of a canal from the Nile to the Red Sea. He had sufficient power to proclaim:

I am a Persian; setting out from Persia I conquered Egypt. I ordered to dig this canal from the river that is called Nile and flows in Egypt, to the sea that begins in Persia. Therefore, when this canal had been dug as I had ordered, ships went from Egypt through this canal to Persia, as I had intended.

Connecting the two seas – and thereby shortening the distance around the southern tip of Africa – was an imaginative but imperfect concept. It was finally abandoned in the eighth century AD (not so much for maintenance issues but because it allowed enemy shipping to enter from the south) and the idea was not revived again until Ferdinand de Lesseps masterminded the construction of the Suez Canal. This modern waterway was to change the geography not only of the region but also the pattern of international shipping. It now accounts for the transport of about 12% of world trade.

When traffic through the canal is impeded, it affects not only the flow of world trade but also the ability of Egypt to collect much-needed revenue from ships passing through.

- ◆ Then there is the considerable length of the sea itself. Apart from its commercial importance, along its shores there is now a scattering of tourist resorts, for most of the year enjoying hot but not unbearable temperatures. It has become popular for its water sports and the attraction of exceptional marine biodiversity. From the various beaches, ships can be seen sailing in both directions, far enough away to cause no problems for leisure users but near enough to offer their own source of interest. This benign natural setting, however, has largely hidden the fact that, in strategic terms, it is also extremely vulnerable; in late-2023, this vulnerability was sharply revealed. The fact is that ships passing through can be attacked by rockets from either bank. It is the Houthis in Yemen which to date have exploited this but there are other sources of instability in the nations facing the sea; Eritrea and Sudan are themselves far from stable.
- ◆ Finally, in the south, the Bab el-Mendeb forces shipping into a chokepoint close to the adjacent shores. And even if it emerges unscathed from its journey through the Red Sea, there are further ‘hot points’ to take into account:

- ◇ One is the risk of pirate action spreading from Somalia into the Gulf of Aden.
- ◇ Another is the fact that the previously impoverished state of Djibouti is now home to more military bases per square mile than anywhere else in the world. If just one external nation is drawn into the conflict, the intervention could quickly spread.
- ◇ Finally, the breakaway (and presently unrecognized) state of Somaliland has stoked the fires through an agreement with Ethiopia to provide direct access to the Indian Ocean. Berbera is the name of the port which makes good sense in economic terms but not without antagonizing neighbouring states (including Somalia and Eritrea).

In other words, Seychelles would do well to monitor events in the Horn of Africa, any one of which could affect shipping routes and alliances in the region.

The delicacy of diplomacy

Seychelles might have chosen to look away from evolving events and at first it seemed to do just that. In a UN vote on 26 October 2023, on the issue of humanitarian aid and an immediate cease-fire in Gaza, the small-island state took the unusual step of absenting itself from the meeting of the General Assembly when the vote was taken. Rightly or wrongly, the action was interpreted as Seychelles being unsure of its stance and not wishing to offend different interests. However, when a further resolution was brought forward on 12 December 2023, it cast its vote in favour. Both motions were opposed by Israel on the grounds that a cease-fire would benefit Hamas. As the votes were non-binding, they had no effect on what was happening on the ground, but it undoubtedly brought into question the neutrality of Seychelles. Was this the point when Seychelles lost its innocence, or had it already done so?

A further example of partisanship – although this time ostensibly favouring the critics of Hamas – came at the end of 2023, when Houthi rebels in northern Yemen started to fire rockets at merchant shipping passing through the Red Sea. The declared aim was to target ships bound for Israel but this soon became less discriminate, causing the major shipping companies to take the longer and more expensive route around the southern tip of Africa. In an effort to control the situation, America took the initiative in forming a multinational naval team – with the strange title of Operation Prosperity Guardian – intended mainly for the sharing of information and not for the deployment of physical assets. Alongside bigger players like the UK, Canada and France, Seychelles agreed to be a member.

The rationale for Seychelles joining the naval team was that it already belonged to an existing security network, Combined Maritime Forces, an international anti-piracy coalition in the region. Its action may have seemed logical enough but for supporters of the Houthi rebels it was interpreted almost as an act of war. Hezbollah leader, Hassan

Nasrallah was quick to condemn the US-led response in the Red Sea, and mocked the inclusion of Seychelles. 'It is the smallest country in Africa', he said, 'and not known for having a powerful navy'. He claimed ignorance of Seychelles – 'Senshel, Menshel, whatever its name is', and added that he had to Google the location of the island state. Fearing reprisals, it seems that a number of Seychellois hoped that he was unsuccessful in finding it, with a petition calling on the government to reverse its support for the American-led organization. But by then the die was cast and the country found itself in a new arena.

Reflecting its politicization, on 27 January 2024, a march was arranged through the streets of Victoria to protest against the Israeli invasion of Gaza. A spokesperson for the march explained that the purpose was to show solidarity with the Palestinian cause. He also took issue with the stance of Seychelles in joining Operation Prosperity Guardian, claiming that the country's involvement raises questions about its alignment with human rights principles and international law. It seems that Victoria already occupies a place in the Middle East.

Resetting the compass?

Seychelles has travelled a long way since independence, even further from the first permanent settlement in 1770, and on an altogether different scale since Gondwanaland. Perhaps it hasn't quite landed up in the Middle East but my argument is that it continues to head in that direction.

In the spirit of this discussion, is this a view that has support? And, if so, are there other factors to take into account? Are things as they always were or has the situation already changed? Where, in short, is Seychelles now located and how has it come to occupy this strategic position? Is the small island nation transitioning from past neutrality to partisanship and, if so, is it already within a war zone?

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